

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract. Today, the importance of digital technology is growing in society. Their widespread introduction and the development of the digital economy have become a serious life issue for each country in modern times. Experts believe that by digitizing the economy in the next 3 years, 22% of the world's jobs will be created using information technology.

Keywords: Digital economy, digitalization, digital governance, economy, market economy, digital marketing, digital technology.

ЦИФРОВЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ – ВАЖНЫЙ ФАКТОР ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА

Аннотация. Сегодня значение цифровых технологий в обществе возрастает. Их широкое внедрение и развитие цифровой экономики стали серьезной жизненной проблемой для каждой страны в современное время. Эксперты считают, что за счет цифровизации экономики в ближайшие 3 года 22% рабочих мест в мире будут созданы с использованием информационных технологий.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, цифровизация, цифровое управление, экономика, рыночная экономика, цифровой маркетинг, цифровые технологии.

In our President's address to the Supreme Court, the active transition to the digital economy has been identified as one of the most important tasks in the next five years. It is also notable that this year has been declared the Year of Science, Education and Digital Economy Development.

"The digital economy primarily makes it possible to work in a corruption-free area," she says. He is the main cousin of the "corrupt economy." Because the numbers seal everything, keep them in memory. Provides information quickly when necessary. "In such a situation, it will not be possible to hide information, make secret deals, and not provide full information about it or this activity," says Shuhrat Sodiqov. "As a result," she says, "the legal funds directed to the economy will be spent on place. In particular, the timely calculation and payment of taxes, the transparency of budget distribution, socially oriented funds, schools, hospitals, and roads will set the stage for the purposeful reach of their destination. Therefore, it would be a very reasonable and fair description to call digital technology the shortest route to development.

Over the past two years, the Ministry of Information Technology and Communication Development has carried out extensive and comprehensive work. At the same time, today the Ministry has important tasks outlined in the Application.

The main task is **to implement the concept of "Digital Uzbekistan 2030"**, which covers all sectors and networks. Implementing such a large-scale project will ensure complete and comprehensive change in the economy of our country and ensuring competitiveness. Another important task is to ensure the implementation of the decision of our country's leader "on measures to expand the development of digital technologies in Tashkent." The comprehensive "Digital Tashkent" program, approved by the resolution, aims to fully change the appearance of our capital, involving information and communication technologies in education, health care, transportation, and communal fields.

The concept of "Digital Tashkent" is directly related to the large-scale "Safe City" project, which stipulated the need to implement it gradually throughout the republic between 2019 and 2023. In the first phase, work is under way to create a single technological platform for the project in Tashkent.

On April 28, this year, the President adopted a resolution "on measures to expand the digital economy and e-government." According to him, by 2023, the digital economy is expected to double its share of the country's gross domestic product and 3 times the volume of services in this area and increase their exports to \$100 million. At the same time, between 2020 and 2022, 268 projects are planned to be implemented to further develop the technological park of electronic government, telecommunications, software products and information technology, and to expand the development of digital technologies in real sector sectors of the economy and in agriculture and water management.

The performance of these tasks will have a significant impact on the socio-economic development of our country.

"How is the process of digitizing agriculture, one of the most relevant areas for our country?"

"There is a special emphasis on the widespread introduction of digital technologies in areas of great importance for development in Uzbekistan," she says. Agriculture plays an important role in this list. Therefore, it is intended to implement 24 projects that will help bring networks to a new phase. Needless to say, there are few problems with the introduction of digital technologies in agricultural and water industries, as well as issues that need to be resolved quickly. Information technology is very useful in accounting and monitoring land in agriculture. For example, by cosmic zonding of the earth, you can study crops, the vegetation process, the meliorative state of the earth, and the amount of mineralization. This will clearly define agricultural measures and increase productivity by 25-30%.

An experimental (pilot) project is being undertaken to use satellite data to quickly and accurately evaluate the state of agricultural land in the province of Anchorage and the crops produced in them. As part of the project, six fields in the region will be selected and placed on the online platform "Monterra" in vector format. Landowners will also be given appropriate conclusions on the state of crops using satellite technologies.

To implement this project, a new resident will be formed before the Andijan Technopark. Seven qualified programmers will be trained in agriculture.

Analytical information of all crops in the region is compiled and provided to landowners by the established enterprise. In addition, within the framework of the project, it will be possible to export this service, forming relevant conclusions about landfills of foreign countries.

"One of the most important factors in the sustainable development of information and communication technologies is the creation of adequate conditions for market participants," she says. What opportunities have been created for ACT entrepreneurs today?

"Today," she says, "much is being done to create conditions for industry professionals, to develop startup projects in IT entrepreneurship, especially in the field of ICT. For this purpose, a technological park for software products and information technology was established. Currently, 392 organizations employing four thousand specialists are residents of an IT park."

The park has the necessary infrastructure, including modern laboratories, a coworking center and office spaces. Technopark residents are provided with financial, marketing, legal and other consulting services. Another important point is that financial benefits for residents are also set. Such a successful experience led to the opening of technoparks in other parts of our country. Between 2020 and 2024, an IT park will be established in 14 regions of our country, primarily in Nukus, Bukhara, Namangan, Samarkand, Guliston and Urgench, including the specialized school named after al-Khwarizmi in Tashkent. Joint resolutions were signed with local governments on the organization of regional branches of the IT park, and network schedules for each project were approved.

The branch office of Jehovah's Witnesses **in Brooklyn**, New York, U.S.A. One of them was opened on June 30 in Guliston, Syrdarya region, the Gulistan branch of the Technological Park for Software Products and Information Technologies was opened. The necessary measures are being taken to further develop the technological park of software products and information technology. These include expanding the activities that can be introduced by technopark residents, expanding digital education centers in regions, and implementing information technology in socio-economic so socio-economic so so as to attract technopark residents.

From this point of view, the granting of government agencies the right to sign contracts worth **up to \$1 billion (U.S.)** on a competitive basis among IT park residents in order to increase and support the number of manufacturers of local software products opens the door to new opportunities for talented young people and encourages them to new ideas.

"What are the advantages of digital technology for the population? " What urgent tasks are needed to provide convenient online public services for citizens?

"The **Single portal of interactive government services** (<https://my.gov.uz>) has been developed to further develop contactless forms of communication between the population and business entities with government agencies. Today, there are more than 176 electronic public services available through the Single portal.

To improve the quality and speed of organizing the work of entrepreneurs, including foreign investors, to ensure open and direct communication with them, to implement their legal requirements practically and effectively, and to solve problematic issues, the "business.gov.uz" portal **of the Prime Minister's virtual reception for reviewing applications from businesspeople** has been launched.

A single electronic system "project.gov.uz" has been introduced to review draft regulations to all interested ministries, agencies, and executive authorities, to agree using an electronic signature, including to conduct simultaneous discussions of the general public and experts and to significantly exceed the time and labour resources for quick shipment.

In addition, services have been created for licensing passengers and freight transportation services, accepting documents from applicants online, receiving government subsidies for mortgage loans, and obtaining certificates from the place of study.

One of the highlights of the establishment of an effective system of communication between government agencies and the population is the **"My Opinion" Portal of Collective Appeals**. Currently, the web portal has received more than 3.6 thousand applications, **more than 25,2 thousand** suggestions and comments have been published.

On the Single interactive state services portal, **26 new services** are launched, the total number of services **exceeds 200**. Since the beginning of the year, **1.4 million** electronic services have been provided, an increase of **8.1%** over the same period last year .

At the same time, a list of **50** popular public services to be introduced on the Single portal has been approved by the end of the year.

If we hit them, online enrollment in a doctor's office, electronic registration of a newborn child in a clinic, registration of real estate lease agreements, registration of architectural and planning assignments, registration of cadastre passports, sending applications for benefits, receiving state subsidy on mortgage loans, permanent registration of citizens in The City of Tashkent and The Tashkent region, An archive certificate and other services on confirming the work experience will be introduced.

The interdepartmental platform of electronic government establishes the electronic communication of about 90 information systems and resources of government agencies, and **more than 160 million** requests are provided with information online.

A presentation before our country's administrator on June 8, this year on the implementation of reforms in the development of information technology and the digital economy emphasized the importance of quickly transferring the most necessary public services to electronic form.

Today, demand for the digital economy, the "Electronic Government" services, is increasing day by day. However, only **780 types of** public services are now available through the "electronic portal" **in all 185**. In most organizations, digitizing the work process is limited only to electronic exchange of documents. In this regard, further development of e-government, provision of modern convenient state services for citizens is of particular importance. In order to accelerate this process, it is planned to implement **104 projects covering the most important directions and current issues**.

For example, the introduction of the "**Foreign Electronic Medical Card**" information system in the health care system will help to develop a single medical database on the citizens of our country and to monitor the health of the population. The information system "**Electronic prescription**" is a project aimed at organizing effective and safe treatment of patients with medical means, the formation of an electronic registry of doctors. This, in turn, will help improve the system of monitoring and monitoring medical equipment.

Information systems "**Electronic Clinic**" and "**Electronic Hospital**" are also intended to improve the quality of medical services by creating an innovative computerized system in medical institutions.

"About 60% of the population of Uzbekistan are young people," she says, "and providing them with jobs by expanding their involvement in modern information technology, creating software products, and providing outsourcing services is one of the most important tasks. What measures are being taken to prepare textbooks for the ACT industry in this regard?

"The greatest asset in Uzbekistan is young people, who make up more than half of their population," she says. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Therefore, increasing the quality of life of our young people in society has been elevated to the rise of government policy and there is a great deal of emphasis on their acquisition of new specialties and professions.

In December 2019, the modern building of the school, which specializes in deepening and teaching subjects related to the ICT route named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, was commissioned to be used. Currently, 680 children who have successfully passed exams in mathematics and foreign languages are enrolled in 5-11 classes of this school.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi has also made significant changes in education. Since the 2018/2019 academic year, the university has been transferred to the credit system of modern education, with 9,609 students currently studying in this system. Joint Uzbek-Belarusian faculty was also established in the structure of the university.

In October 2019, the university opened an innovative educational media center with a technical grant of **\$1.6 million** from the Japan International Cooperation Organization (JICA). The media center has every chance to capture and produce a videoconferency.

During that time, the University of Inha in Tashkent also worked effectively to develop international relations. In March 2019, the first "**ASPEX BI SCHOOL**" school for the training of business analysts in Uzbekistan was opened at the university.

There is a special emphasis on teaching IT basics among young people and creating the necessary conditions for them to learn in this direction. Within the framework of the "**Five Initiatives**" programme, the Ministry has implemented efforts to organize the effective use of computer technologies and the Internet by the population and young people.

The Digital Technologies Training Center was established, creating new jobs. In addition, the University of Amiti in Tashkent was established. World experience shows that high goals in the field of information technology can be achieved by accelerating the process of preparing modern developers. Therefore, in order to fill the existing gap, the project "One Million Programmer" was launched.

Today, as part of the "**One Million Programmers**" project, classes are conducted through the uzbekcoders.uz learning portal. It provides free video courses in the top four majors in demand, including data analysis, android apps, web applications and software development classes with subtitles in English.

To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a **brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide** has been prepared.

For example, during the 2020/2021 academic year, more **than 47,000 students from more than 2.1,000 schools** and **more than 54,000 students from 44 higher education institutions** are planned to be trained through the uzbekcoders.uz portal.

Also, starting in the 2020/2021 academic year, work is under way to include topics of programming in higher and secondary schools as part of the "One Million Programmer" project in relevant fields of engineering and information technology in secondary schools. Digital technology training centers have been established throughout our country for residents and young people. The Ministry of Information Technology and Communication Development plans to open at least **100 digital technology training centers in** all regions . Short-term training courses will be launched in such areas as programming foundations, electronic commerce, and graphic design.

Another important innovation is that now specialized schools will be established by the district branches of the IT park under the Ministry of Information Technology and

Communication Development to deepen and teach information and communication technologies in each district and city. In **more than 200** cities and districts of our country, one school has been selected and specializes in the field of information and communication technology. These schools serve as a key base in the field of information and communication technology for other schools in districts and cities. Informatics will help teachers improve their skills and collaborate on new projects.

Instead, the launch of such large-scale projects will rapidly increase the role and role of digital technology in our lives during the year of the development of science, education, and the digital economy and their coverage throughout our country. The system is constantly developing, large-scale and complex projects are being implemented. At the same time, we still have important tasks ahead of us that need to be accomplished.

After all, the development of Uzbekistan is inextricably linked to the introduction and application of digital technologies in all sectors and networks.

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